

Extended Order Generalized Integral Control based Circulating Current Mitigating Scheme in Modular Multi Level Converters- A Balancing Approach

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Abstract—In Modular Multilevel Converters (MMC), circulating currents consist of both DC and AC components. However, these currents are significantly affected by even harmonic distortions, which introduce ripples in the Sub-Module (SM) capacitor voltages. These ripples contribute to the circulating currents, increasing the voltage stress on the SM switches and adversely impacting overall system performance. This paper presents a systematic approach to mitigating circulating currents by employing an Extended Order Generalized Integrator (EOGI), which effectively removes even harmonic components from the converter's legs. The proposed solution has been evaluated against existing methods and demonstrated to offer enhanced robustness in the face of parameter uncertainties and sudden load variations. The scheme was initially validated using MATLAB/Simulink, with further real-time performance verification conducted via OPAL-RT simulation and experiments, yielding promising results.

Index Terms—Modular multilevel converter, Circulating current control, Rotating reference frame, PI control

NOMENCLATURE

<i>CHB</i>	Cascaded H-Bridge Converter
<i>CPS – PWM</i>	Carrier Phase-Shifted PWM
<i>EMI</i>	Electromagnetic Interference
<i>EOGI</i>	Extended Order Generalized Integrator
<i>ESR</i>	Equivalent Series Resistance
<i>FCC</i>	Flying Capacitor Clamped Converter
<i>HIL</i>	Hardware-in-the-Loop
<i>HVDC</i>	High Voltage Direct Current
<i>ISE</i>	Integral Square Error
<i>MMC</i>	Modular Multilevel Converter
<i>NLM</i>	Nearest Level Modulation
<i>NPC</i>	Neutral Point Clamped Converter
<i>PWM</i>	Pulse Width Modulation
<i>RL</i>	Resistive-Inductive Load
<i>SHE</i>	Selective Harmonic Elimination
<i>STATCOM</i>	Static Synchronous Compensator
<i>THD</i>	Total Harmonic Distortion

I. INTRODUCTION

Modular multilevel converters (MMCs) have revolutionized high-power electronic systems, particularly in medium- to high-voltage applications such as HVDC transmission, grid integration of renewable energy, and industrial motor drives. Their modular architecture, which replaces centralized DC-link capacitors with distributed submodules (SMs) containing individual capacitors, enables unparalleled scalability, efficiency, and fault tolerance. Unlike conventional multilevel converters—such as Neutral Point Clamped (NPC),

Cascaded H-Bridge (CHB), and Flying Capacitor Clamped (FCC) topologies—MMCs eliminate the need for bulky transformers and complex voltage balancing circuits, achieving direct high-voltage operation with minimal Electro Magnetic Interference (EMI) and reduced filter requirements [1, 2]. This modularity allows MMCs to scale seamlessly to voltages exceeding hundreds of kilovolts, a feat impractical for traditional converters due to limitations in semiconductor device ratings and thermal management [4, 5].

While NPC, CHB, and FCC converters are widely used in industrial applications, they face inherent challenges in high-voltage scenarios. NPC and FCC converters suffer from uneven voltage distribution across semiconductor switches, necessitating complex balancing circuits that increase system cost and complexity. CHB converters, though modular, require isolated DC sources via multiple secondary winding transformers, which escalate spatial and financial overheads. These constraints restrict their operational voltage to 6–13.8 kV, making them unsuitable for ultra-high-voltage applications like HVDC transmission, where series-connected switches would introduce prohibitive insulation and cooling challenges [3, 4, 5].

Introduced by R. Marquardt in 2001 [6], MMCs address these limitations by distributing energy storage across SMs, each comprising a capacitor and switches (e.g., half-bridge or full-bridge configurations). This design enables direct connection to high-voltage grids without line-frequency transformers, significantly reducing footprint and cost. MMCs are now integral to modern power systems, including offshore wind farms, STATCOMs, and cross-continental HVDC links [7, 8, 9]. However, their operation introduces unique control challenges, primarily stemming from the dynamic interaction between SMs. Key issues include:

- 1) **Submodule Capacitor Voltage Balancing:** Fluctuations during charging/discharging cycles create voltage ripple, affecting output waveform quality.
- 2) **Circulating Currents:** Arm current imbalances generate even-order harmonics (e.g., 2nd, 4th), increasing switch stress, losses, and instability risks.
- 3) **Output Current Regulation:** Managing grid synchronization under variable loads and grid faults.

Circulating currents in MMCs arise from voltage mismatches between the upper and lower arms of each phase leg. These currents, dominated by negative-sequence components